

Grammar Translation and Bilingual Methods as Methods of Teaching

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Abstract: This article provides useful and effective information on how to improve speaking and communication skills, which are one of the most important aspects in the process of learning English, using different methodologies. In the process of learning a language, especially English, and being able to communicate effectively in that language, the role of listening, reading and writing skills is of course also invaluable. Useful information about its important role in increasing Also, the effective organization of the language teaching process depends to a large extent on the teachers, that is, this article provides useful information about how to teach the grammar of that language.

Keywords: Grammar Translation Method, first language, second language, direct approach, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), English for Specific Purposes (ESP), language acquisition, verbal communication, linguistic proficiency, visual aids.

The teacher utilized the Grammar Translation Method to instruct young children, wherein the teacher elucidated each word to the students in their native language to facilitate comprehension and acquisition of English. However, this approach had a drawback. Both the teacher and the student focused more on the first language (L1) rather than the second language (L2). Consequently, the English language class appeared more like an L1 class rather than an L2 class. Students derived only limited benefits from this method.

Regrettably, this method is still prevalent in numerous rural schools across India. It is also supported by the techniques employed to teach the mother tongue in our schools. Perhaps we should proclaim this as our preferred method in our schools. Most teachers adopt the bilingual method to instruct students in Indian schools, where the teacher initially explains the entire English sentence in L1 and then instructs the students to engage in activities in English. It is assumed that only the teachers have the liberty to utilize L1, while students are not expected to employ it. However, this restriction is mostly observed on paper rather than in the classroom. When students are composing their English sentences, they receive ample assistance with mother tongue sentences. This method does not foster fluency and naturalness in language expression. Consequently, this method only proves beneficial to students in learning the second language to a certain extent.¹

In the past, teachers used to follow the direct approach to educate Indian students mainly in private schools, which typically charge a higher tuition fee. These teachers would strictly use only English, without depending on L1. In this case, the teacher is not allowed to use any word from L1. This strict restriction caused students from many families with no background of learning or using English to have great difficulty in understanding certain words and their meanings. However, this method turned out to be

¹ Bailey, K.M. (2005). *Practical English Language Teaching: Speaking*. New York: McGraw-Hill. Faculty of Arts, (2004). Undergraduate catalog. Nacho Pathos, Thailand: SilpakornUniversity Press.

more beneficial for the students to learn the language than any other method as it creates a more conducive language environment for students in the classroom.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a method of teaching English. The principle of CLT is that the English language is best learned through the process of trying to communicate. On the other hand, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a branch of English language teaching (ELT). English for specific purposes implies language for specific purposes, particularly functional purposes (Robinson, 1980). The goal and purpose determine the language needed, the specific skills required, and the range of functions to be performed in the language for a specific area or related to fields like aviation, engineering, law, medicine, tourism, etc. ESP refers to the teaching and learning of English for an instrumental purpose, work, or study-related.² ESP aims to provide learners with the specific semantic abilities necessary for a particular field of study or profession. It is not intended for general purposes, but rather focuses on developing core English language skills. The ultimate goal of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and ESP in English instruction is to achieve overall language proficiency in learners.

Effective communication is a fundamental aspect of any language. The communicative approach emphasizes the practical application of English language skills rather than rote memorization. The importance of communicative competence has been undervalued and is now widely recognized as essential for using English in various language functions. It is believed that language proficiency acquired through different language functions may contribute to the mastery of a new language, leading to effective communication. As Leonard Newark stated, “language acquisition cannot simply be additive; complex language elements are learned as a whole” (Leonard Newark, 1969)

The Bangalore project has implemented a “communicational methodology” where a natural control of language is used instead of a predetermined control. Instead of following a syllabus, learners are given tasks to complete, which are chosen and organized by the instructor’s intuition. Each approach has its own advantages and disadvantages in helping learners acquire English language and communication skills.

Communication is the interaction between two or more individuals. Vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar are key components of verbal communication. It serves as a means of expressing ideas and thoughts, and plays a crucial role in the teaching and learning processes. The components of verbal communication include listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Listening is the primary component of communication and holds great importance. It is considered an art and is performed with the ears. It is estimated that sixty percent of daily communication time is spent on listening. Listening involves being aware, gathering information, and perceiving. The role of the listener is to receive information, decode it, and interpret it. Good listening skills help the recipient of a message understand it and respond accordingly. As Raymundo mentioned, “True listening is the experience of being fully understood by another person. True listening is understanding not just the words being said, but also the meaning behind the words”.³

Speaking is the earliest and most common way to exchange information from one person to another. It plays a significant role in human life and is the quickest form of communication. Speaking involves orally delivering a message to an individual or a group of people. It is essential for spreading information quickly. The speaker must have a thorough understanding of the concept and language that the audience can comprehend. Effective speaking is clear and impactful in order to make the message easy to understand and interpret.

Writing is a means of conveying a message with a purpose. It demonstrates the writer’s ability to think clearly and communicate effectively. Writing is a fundamental aspect of communication. The purpose of writing is to provide information or explain a concept. The writing process involves conveying a message

² Baker, S.C., Macintyre, P.D., 2000. The role of gender and immersion in communication and second language orientations. *Language Learning* 50, 311–341.

³ Brookfield, S.D., & Reskill, S. (1999). *Discussion as a Way of Teaching: Tools and Techniques for Democratic Classrooms*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers.

through letters and symbols. Written communication allows for control over the message. Writing requires mastery of various skills such as language, style, tone, and more. Written technical tools encompass a wide range of different forms, including memos, postings, reports, letters, presentations, resumes, and more. Raymundo asserts that “Writing is a bridge between the mind of the writer and that of his reader” — “communication”.

In my article, I have observed that many students received their schooling and intermediate education in regional medium schools, where they have limited opportunities to practice English for communication and language development. On the other hand, some students from the same group attended English medium schools for twelve years and studied English as a subject, but still struggle to effectively communicate in English due to lack of confidence and feeling embarrassed about their language skills. These obstacles hinder the students from acquiring proficiency in English.

Despite these challenges, students must acquire knowledge in their respective fields through technological resources such as books, periodicals, abstracts, reports, and journals. They need to engage with scientific content, interpret data and theories, and stay updated on technological advancements. To do so, learners must utilize various skills like listening, speaking, reading, and writing to analyze information, grasp key concepts, gather and convey information, present ideas, discuss topics, learn specific vocabulary, distinguish important from less important information, and identify relevant and irrelevant details. Developing a high level of strategic competence in the technical domain is essential, and this should be built upon linguistic and communicative competence.

It is widely acknowledged that language is comprised of individual words and the combination of these words forms coherent sentences. For individuals learning a new language, the primary objective is to develop linguistic proficiency for effective communication. Consequently, English teachers prioritize equipping learners with knowledge of diverse vocabulary and its appropriate usage. Additionally, employing interactive games can facilitate the teaching of fundamental grammar concepts to students using different structures.

Here is an example for lower intermediate students:

Target structure: simple past. Words: bought, ran, ate, pen, smiled and walked.

Example sentences:

Bought: He taught English.

Ran: She made a flan.

Ate: She was called Kate.

Pen: He was called Ken.

Car: They walked far.

Walked: They talked and talked.

➤ Here is a difficult example to practice the present perfect:

A list of six words such as pen, chair, dog, dictionary, travel agent and bus is provided.

Students should make sentences using the present perfect tense that contains a rhyming word.

Hat: She has become fat.

Chair: I have been to the fair.

Dog: He has burnt a log.

Dictionary: I have played Pictionary. (Ref 3)

In addition to the above mentioned methods of learning language. Teachers should focus the learners

towards the individual as well as group activities to practice and use the acquired vocabulary and grammatical patterns according to the situation and the task assigned.

Pretends are the critical assignment that help the learners to enhance the essential practical English of the learners. In pretends, the learners will be relegated a nonexistent part to act and talk appropriately. In this sort of exercises instructors assume an indispensable part to teach and guide the understudies to utilize the proper dialect and perform to meet the circumstance.⁴

Visual aids are a creative method used by educators to teach language to students. It involves the distribution of visual aids such as photos of people, places, or things to groups of six to eight learners. The learners are then given a specific amount of time to remember or study the information related to the provided visuals. Subsequently, the learners are required to discuss the assigned visual aids.

This approach helps expand the learners' analytical skills. Ultimately, the learners will strive to use the appropriate vocabulary relevant to the visual aids and enhance their sentence structure to come up with innovative ideas. It contributes to language learning. The facilitator or educator must encourage students to speak freely.

Due to the global trends in English language learning, educators now focus more on interactive approaches rather than traditional lecturing. Their main aim is to develop students into effective English communicators both in and out of the classroom.

To accomplish this, they include the understudies to partake more in classroom exercises with the goal that they will obtain sufficient summon over talking abilities. To make this environment, instructors can direct gathering discourses, where understudies should talk just in English. Here, they can give their perspectives, thoughts and musings in English because of which they build up the propensity for talking smoothly in English as they do in their primary language.⁵

Various types of examinations also assist students in enhancing their overall awareness and understanding of current affairs. It provides ample scope for imagination and deep thoughts. Such discussions enable students to listen to the perspectives of their peers, thereby helping them gain knowledge and improve their vocabulary as well. Debates also play a crucial role in enhancing students' speaking abilities, both at school and at a higher level. Debates not only encourage students to speak confidently and fluently but also help them take a stance and remain firm and resolute in their opinions. In addition to this advantage of critical thinking, it provides students with the experience of controlling their emotions without losing their temper. It also helps them organize their thoughts and ideas, especially while speaking.

The need of the hour for learners is to meet the challenges of modern-day competition in this world. Learning English plays a major role in facing these challenges. In order to improve language learning, English should not be treated merely as a subject but should be effectively used in communication with people around the world. By using traditional methods, a significant portion of class time is wasted on exercises and drills focusing on grammar and pronunciation. These methods were mainly used to develop basic language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing, but by following these methods, listening and speaking skills were neglected as students were unable to put their language into practice.

In the period of focused world, where most of the understudies are endeavoring GRE and TOEFL, great listening and talking aptitudes turn into an outright need.

Open methodology was completely dismissed by educators and learners which has turned into a worldwide interest where understudies should convey over the globe. Instructors ought to go about as facilitators, and ought to watch how well understudies arrange their contemplations while talking with their kindred individuals.

⁴ C.S., "communication", Himalaya publication house page no 144 art of listening)

⁵ Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. *Applied Linguistics*, 1-1, 1-47.

As dialect changes topographically because of persuasive varieties, the educator ought to find a way to instruct their understudy about impartial accent and their significance while correspondence. Clear articulation, not flawless elocution, is the objective.

Understudies are likewise now encouraged by programming to practice articulation through phonetics. To accomplish the objectives of dialect adapting today every school ought to be furnished with dialect lab, complex hardware like PCs, LCD Projectors.

Notwithstanding these, our staff too ought to redesign their insight, aptitudes and ought to obtain careful quality over their syllabus to meet the requests of globalization since English is seen as a key instructive interest in this world. In the event that furnished with the most recent dialect showing devices and with the backing of innovation, one can instruct the dialect adequately and rouse the understudies towards dialect learning.

1. Bailey, K.M. (2005). *Practical English Language Teaching: Speaking*. New York: McGraw-Hill. Faculty of Arts, (2004). Undergraduate catalog. Nacho Pathos, Thailand: SilpakornUniversity Press.
2. Baker, S.C., Macintyre, P.D., 2000. The role of gender and immersion in communication and second language orientations. *Language Learning* 50, 311–341.
3. Brookfield, S.D., & Reskill, S. (1999). *Discussion as a Way of Teaching: Tools and Techniques for Democratic Classrooms*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers.
4. Brown, G., & Yule, G. (1983). *Teaching the spoken language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. C.S., “communication”, Himalaya publication house page no 144 art of listening)
6. Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. *Applied Linguistics*, 1–1, 1–47.
7. Bailey, K.M. (2005). *Practical English Language Teaching: Speaking*. New York: McGraw-Hill. Faculty of Arts, (2004). Undergraduate catalog. Nacho Pathos, Thailand: SilpakornUniversity Press.
8. Baker, S.C., Macintyre, P.D., 2000. The role of gender and immersion in communication and second language orientations. *Language Learning* 50, 311–341.
9. Brookfield, S.D., & Reskill, S. (1999). *Discussion as a Way of Teaching: Tools and Techniques for Democratic Classrooms*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers.